

DESIGN PERSPECTIVES ON SAFETY ISSUES IN SOCIETY. AN EXPLORATION OF KEY ELEMENTS OF DESIGN PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Our society is confronted with a wide variety of safety related issues in the public domain that affect personal and public well-being. Only recently designers are involved in many of these social safety related projects. The goal of this paper is to explore the essence of this design perspective on social safety. For this purpose, we first identify three key elements of design practice that are considered fundamental for design's ability to deal with open, complex and dynamic problems in general: (1) proposing future solutions, (2) developing problem situations and (3) creating frames. Next, the adoption of these design elements within the context of social safety design problems are explored and described. These explorative cases provide insights into the design perspective on social safety and the potential contribution of design practice to this problem area.

Keywords: Social safety, design practice, designing-out-crime.

INTRODUCTION

Our current society is confronted with a wide variety of crime related issues in the public domain that affect personal and public well-being. These issues range from the relatively innocent problems of bicycle theft and loitering teens to the more serious threats of terrorism. Crime is on the rise, but the public and political attention has grown even more. However, the main development in the '90's is the transformation of crime into a social safety issue, as described by Boutellier. "Crime is no longer a matter involving offenders, victims, the police and courts, it involves everyone and any number of agencies and institutions from security companies to local authorities and from schools to pub and restaurant

owners" (2004). Over the past decades safety has become a main theme within our society.

Although the increasing attention for these social safety problems is a sign of the times, most of these problems have existed for ages (Wilson and Herrnstein, 1998). Many policy-makers, criminologists and urban planners have invested time and effort into the reduction of crime. Within these professional areas, the design-affects-crime debate has received considerable attention over the past decades (Cozens et al., 2001). Methods like Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) and Situational Crime Prevention (SCP) adopt design approaches to prevent that an object or place is being targeted (Cozens et al., 2005; Clarke, 1992). However, within these fields, design is mainly restricted to the development of general safety guidelines and technology-based countermeasures like surveillance (e.g. lighting and CCTV) and target hardening (vandalism proof products). Despite a large and growing body of research that supports the assertion that CPTED is a pragmatic and effective crime prevention tool, there is no definitive (empirical) proof (Cozens et al., 2005).

Next to these technology-based approaches, there is a more sociological approach to social safety problems that focuses social integration. Theory building on neighborhoods, communities and social cohesion has a long history in social policy and sociology. These issues were at the core of sociology in the first half of the 20th century (Forrest and Kearns, 2001). The increasing urbanization of this period was seen to be producing a social order in which the traditional ties of community—shared space, close kinship links, shared religious and moral values—were being replaced by anonymity,

individualism and competition (Forrest and Kearns, 2001). Since this period, social capital and neighborhoods are constant returning subjects in social safety debates. Moreover, the aspiration of creating ‘local communities’ is supported by Putnam’s claim that researchers in diverse fields such as education, urban poverty, unemployment, the control of crime and drug abuse, and even health, have discovered that successful outcomes are more likely in ‘civically engaged communities’ (1995). However, the development of these local communities in order to reduce social unsafety comes at a price for its community members. As Bauman states it, [these communities] “... demand unconditional loyalty and treats everything short of such loyalty as an act of unforgivable treason. ...The price that is paid for the privilege of being ‘in a community’ is paid in the currency of freedom, variously called ‘autonomy’, ‘right to self-assertion’, ‘right to be yourself’ (2001).”

Relatively new in the area of safety is the role and the approach of the designer. Only for this last decade, designers are involved in many safety related projects. Renowned design schools are educating their students ‘Designing Against Crime’ (DAC) and ‘Designing Out Crime’ (DOC) methodology (Designing Against Crime, 2010; Gamman and Pascoe, 2004; Designing Out Crime, 2010). This increased involvement of designers in social safety is in line with the increasing interest of designers to alter behavior (Tromp and Hekkert, 2009; Fogg, 2003; Lockton et al., 2008). The application of design within a social safety context can also be linked to the various application areas of design thinking practices.

At first glance, designers involved in these issues seem to cleverly combine technological as well as social elements in their safety solutions. But as Norman defines it; design creates environments that facilitate and trigger social processes, through the creation of affordances (2002). Design within a safety context is therefore not only concerned with the social part of understanding and influencing social behavior (and discouraging anti-social or criminal behavior) but also with the technological part of creating environments (e.g. products,

systems and services) that trigger this desired behavior. But what are the elements from design practice that designers apply to this type of problems? What is this design perspective on social safety problems? And, what makes the approach of these designers so different from the earlier approaches of their colleague criminologists and sociologists?

The overall goal of this paper is to explore the core value that the design perspective can bring to social safety projects. For this purpose, we will first identify three key elements of the design practice that are considered fundamental for design’s ability to deal with open, complex and dynamic issues like social safety problems. Subsequently, two extensive case-study examples of the adoption of these design elements within the context of social safety design problems are explored and described. We discuss the outcome of this exploration and provide some first insights into the merits and limitations of the design perspective on social safety and the (potential) contribution of design practice to this problem area.

DESIGN PRACTICE

While most social safety problems have existed for ages, the openness, complexity and dynamic character of the problems have increased substantially the last decades. Many important (safety) issues in today’s society have become so complicated that they seem impervious to solution. Most of the ‘traditional’ problem solving strategies work reasonably well in an orderly universe: when problems appear they can be isolated in a relatively separate problem arena, abstracted from the details of the concrete problem situation, the sub-problems decomposed and analyzed, and a conclusion could be reached in due course. If all else fails, authority or power can be used to ‘simplify’ the problem area by overruling some parties and force a solution. But this problem solving strategy does not work for today’s social safety problems: the enclosed ‘mini-world’ of societies, economies and cultures have been replaced by a tangle of relationships within complex overlapping networks, where power does not rest in one place and truth seems to have become a matter of perspective. Different problems are so intimately related to each other (and there are so

many dependencies between these interrelationships) that it is impossible to isolate one. Design practice can inspire alternatives to conventional problem solving strategies especially within the context of these open, complex and networked problem situations. Within these situations problems often manifest themselves as paradoxes.

PARADOXES

A statement or set of statements is paradoxical when not all assumptions can be true together. Common causes for these are: self reference, infinite regress, the inclusion of circular definitions and confusion between levels of abstraction. Unregarded the more theoretical transactions on paradoxes, this paper is concerned with real-world paradoxes that are caused by conflicting values and needs on the problem side, or incommensurability of solutions on the solution side. In these real-world situations, paradoxes are considered to be unresolvable when perceived rationalities are clashing. These perceived rationalities arise when a certain way of defining and thinking about the world is seen as the only one possible. This makes life hard for the problem solver that is caught in the middle because these rationalities are not seen to have contexts, or they pretend not to have them. Without the view on the context of the rationality, there is also no way of seeing the relativity of its assumptions in a particular situation. This is when perceived rationalities become rock-hard, understanding becomes absolute, and so does truth (Lakoff, 1990). The paradox then consists of two absolute truths on a collision course. This head-on approach of problem solving can only lead to compromise.

It is interesting however, to realize how paradoxes can provoke new thoughts, how they capture the creative mind and how people cannot help to start thinking about how to resolve them. A paradox is only completely contradictory in a certain, defined context. Design strategies to move forward from a paradoxical situation are based on the investigation of this context, exploring the core issues and assumptions that underlie the paradox. This is a process of thinking around the paradox rather than confronting it head-on. This is exactly where lessons

can be drawn from design practice. Expert designers have developed practices that are built on the realization that the solution is not in the core paradox itself (that is locked up in closed definitions and unquestionable rationality), but in the broad area of values and themes in the context around the core paradox. The richer the context, the more chance there is that avenues can be found to move forward. This is where the same properties of problem situations that were outlined as the big contemporary challenge to problem solving - open, complex, dynamic - that are hugely problematic for conventional problem solvers, provide a rich field of opportunities to move forward to people with a designerly bent of mind.

KEY ELEMENTS OF DESIGN PRACTICE

There are three key elements of design practice that most clearly address this need to deal with paradoxes underlying today's open, complex and dynamic problems: (1) proposing future solutions, (2) developing problem situations, and (3) creating frames. These key elements will be explained in the following subsections.

PROPOSING FUTURE SOLUTIONS

Design practice aims at the creation of change in the real world. Design professions are inherently action oriented, and oriented towards the future. There is a tendency in design to counter-balance a world that is obsessed with problems and crises to talk about possibilities and futures. The design professions have built up a powerful set of skills and tools to make these possible worlds visible to the decision makers. But apart from the inevitable smoke-and-mirrors, design also has to be realistic: the exploration of possible directions and the proposing of future solutions to test their feasibility are key design activities. They are ongoing activities in any design project, from start to finish. While the ambitions behind a design project may be sky-high, the proposed problem formulation must be seen to be realistic too. Setting the bar too high will just mean that the problem cannot be solved at all. Yet the bar shouldn't be too low either: the problem formulation should inspire interesting new avenues of thought. Getting the balance right is a constant concern within a design practice.

In problem situations where there are multiple stakeholders around the table that are busy disagreeing (they tend to not agree about anything because they represent different value sets and interests), putting a design in front of them creates a natural future-focus to the conversation. People will start criticizing the proposed design rather than disagreeing with each other, thus showing much more clearly where they are coming from. They will recognize themselves in others arguments for and against the design, and coalitions will form quite naturally. The creation of a discussion around a proposed design often has a deeply therapeutic effect on these situations. Some designers that have realized this great quality of their profession, and now make this their core process: they first study a situation to see which discussions should be had among stakeholders, and then create a design proposal that actively sparks those discussions - so the design is not a solution at all, but a very deliberate 'conversation piece'. Apparently, this future orientation of design is a useful strategy to move forward from a paradoxical problem situation.

DEVELOPING PROBLEM SITUATIONS

Often, design practice involves a phase where the problem-as-presented needs to be 'deconstructed' or opened up. Designers have developed a multitude of informal practices to do this (Paton and Dorst, 2010). The 'briefing' that is the start of any design project is not a moment, but an intense phase of negotiation and creative framing of the projected outcomes. Hekkert et al. have developed a formal approach to this for the field of product design (2003). Within their model, the first step involves the critical reflection on the assumptions behind the initial brief or question. To be able to create newness, the designer has to know the type of thinking that led to the current products and the current problem situation. They dig deeply to go back to the fundamentals, and then question the importance of those fundamental variables or their 'settings' in the future. Then they proceed to create an image of the context as it will develop, and start the design process proper, creating an object that will fit that new context. Changing people's minds and helping an organization to develop a closer understanding of the broader situation in which they are a player is

vitaly important in order to escape the paradoxical problem situation.

CREATING FRAMES

Framing is the third key element from design practice that addresses the need to deal with paradoxes. A frame is an organizational principle or a more or less coherent set of statements that are good to think with. Designers start to frame when they are confronted with a paradox during explorations, or when they are engaged in creating progress towards a more or less defined goal. Although, frames can sometimes be summarized by a simple and elegant statement or description, they are rather complex and subtle thought-tools. The proposing of a frame includes the use of certain concepts that are given importance and meaning. These concepts are not neutral at all: they have the potential to start leading the perceptions further on in the process of creation. Within a frame, key concepts are connected in a special way - often characterized or caricatured in a 'lead metaphor'.

The development of a new frame is the result of a broader intentional action; the frame then re-articulates the scope of that intention in new and interesting ways. Frames should therefore also be actionable (have the possibility to lead to solutions). For a frame to really come 'alive' it also has to be inspiring and captivating, immediately lead to mental images in the key people involved. Good frames are coherent, and provide a stable (non-contradictory) basis for further thinking. They are also really robust, in the sense that the image they conjure up in the minds of the designers and stakeholders are sufficiently similar to provide a 'common ground' for the discussion of the problem, as well as possible solutions. Good frames need to be inspiring and original - perhaps not completely new-to-the-world (Amabile, 1996), but at least new to the problem setting. Expert designers use their exploration of themes as a trigger, directing their creative imagination towards new frames. These framing practices are analytical as well as creative. They are an intense form of sense-making, and involve the creative act of giving meaning to some aspects of a complex reality over others.

THE DESIGN PERSPECTIVE ON SOCIAL SAFETY

As mentioned before, social safety problems often manifest themselves as paradoxes. And the previous section presented three key elements of design practice that most clearly address this need to deal with paradoxes underlying today's open, complex and dynamic problems. In order to explore the design perspective on social safety, this section considers the adoption of these key design elements within two social safety design cases. Moreover, based on these cases, it explores the potential contribution of design practice in general to this problem area.

CASE 1: GRASS PASS (EINDHOVEN)

The soft drugs policy in the Netherlands is considered unique in the world. The easiest way to explain this policy is by saying that coffee shops are allowed to sell soft drugs in limited amounts to their customers but it is illegal for them to buy or grow these soft drugs. In other words, the supply of hemp to coffee shops is illegal but the authorities are tolerating it (in Dutch: *gedogen*). This coffee shop policy has been successful in controlling the soft-drug market; the majority of soft drugs in the Netherlands is sold/bought in coffee shops. However, the amount of people using drugs is still slightly growing. And even more concerning is that the number of teenagers using soft drugs is increasing more rapidly. Dutch law enforces a maximum of two coffee shops per police district in the city and a 250-meters minimum distance between coffee shops and schools. This means that all the coffee shops are somewhat spread across the cities. This also corresponds with the original purpose of coffee shops: the supply of soft drugs to a *local public*. Currently the range of people the coffee shop supply goes far beyond a local public especially in Eindhoven. Eindhoven has become a popular spot for international drugs tourists because of its southern geographical location near the borders with Belgium and Germany. Even the mayors of border cities in Belgium are concerned with the soft drug trafficking taking place between their cities and southern Dutch cities like Eindhoven.

In Eindhoven coffee shop owners can make a lot of money. Given the widespread demand for soft drugs

together with a set maximum of 15 coffee shops within the city, high numbers of customers per coffee shop are more or less guaranteed. Since soft drugs are officially illegal, the government cannot raise sales tax on soft drug products. Altogether, the 15 coffee shops in Eindhoven have an estimated turnover between 30 and 50 million euro per year. This lucrativeness of the soft drugs business makes the coffee shops interesting for criminal organizations. In general, coffee shops and coffee shop owners have a bad reputation within the Dutch society; in many cases they are associated with drug trafficking, money laundering and even organized crime.

In order to get more insight into the transactions and the customers of the coffee shops and to limit drugs tourism from surrounding countries the Dutch government announced the introduction of the grass pass. The grass pass would be a registered membership card for coffee shop customers and would be required for buying weed in Dutch coffee shops. The announcement of the introduction of the grass pass resulted in many oppositions among coffee shop owners and customers. Based on these announcements, the city of Eindhoven asked a design student to analyze the coffee shop situation in Eindhoven and to reconsider the current design of the grass pass.

Like many social safety problems, the soft drugs problem is a long existing and complex problem within society. A design student from the faculty of Industrial Design (Eindhoven University of Technology) worked on this project for a complete semester. This student started with a very explicit process of exploring the themes behind the frames of the involved stakeholders. He performed an elaborate stakeholder analysis using mixed methods as interviewing, site (coffee shop) visits, desktop research and observations. A wide range of stakeholders were involved in this early stage of the projects like coffee shop owners and clients, local residents, police, policy makers, soft drugs experts and a representative of the association of coffee shop owners in Eindhoven. The student translated the stakeholder analysis in a cartoonlike drawing expressing the opinions and perspectives of the

different stakeholders. An A0 poster of this drawing was presented to the different stakeholders to provoke a response that would further explicate the underlying frames of the problem (see figure 1). The playful presentation of this stakeholder analysis, unlike traditional problem-focused stakeholder analysis presentations, allowed stakeholders to relate to the different perspectives and opinions represented.

This approach of exploring the context resulted in a detailed understanding of the problem context and the underlying frames of the stakeholders. A very interesting outcome of this process was the insight that currently coffee shops have nothing positive to offer to a neighborhood. Without considering the negative aspects of having a coffee shop in your street, it is very hard to come up with an added value of having such a premise in your street. However, the negative aspects of coffee shops for local residents were also rather different than expected. Unlike the public opinion in which coffee shops are associated with criminal and antisocial behavior, the main problem for to be a parking problem. As a result of neighbors appeared the wide

range of people the coffee shop currently supply, there is a continuous traffic flow of cars and even trucks on these local roads. Moreover, cars are often parked double while their owners just hop in the coffee shop to do a quick purchase of their weekly stash. This overload of the local infrastructure is a major nuisance for these neighborhoods. Based on this first exploration, the student reframed the problem by comparing the Eindhoven's coffee shops with big department stores in contrast to the smaller scale boutique shops you would expect them to be. Currently, the coffee shops are big shops where most people just go to buy their joints and leave directly afterwards. They design of the coffee shop is completely focused on the logistical handling of all these customers.

In order to restore the local function and character of coffee shops the number of coffee shops within the city should be increased instead of decreased. The student proposed a redesign of the coffee shops to express the local character of the premises. The coffee shop is transformed into a coffee cafe where people cannot only buy weed but can also enjoy a good coffee or lunch.

Figure 1. Stakeholder Analysis

The detailed design solution is currently under consideration. However, the overall conceptual experience design of Eindhoven's coffee shops was positively received by the city as an alternative approach to control drug traffic within the city.

CASE 2: GRAFFITI (SYDNEY)

Graffiti is a universal city-issue these days. The conventional ways of dealing with this problem range from CCTV surveillance, the coating surfaces in anti-graffiti paint, protective coating on glass, making sure it the tags and artwork get cleaned off quickly, to setting up elaborate databases to identify and prosecute offenders, and either fine them or even - under new draconian laws- put them in jail. The young DOC designers have approached graffiti as a social and cultural issue, and move away from these physical solutions. This is where the very word Graffiti gets in the way, and a distinction needs to be made between tagging and street art. There are completely different groups of people involved, tagging being a teenage activity that is frowned upon by the street art community. Both taggers and street artists are subcultures with a strong internal value set and strict rules about what is allowed and what not. Breaking the rules results in a public shaming of the perpetrator, often on community blogs and websites. The designers have worked with these communities to find ways of minimizing the impact of their activities, in a clever campaign called 'Think Street'. Temporary structures like the boards around building sites and scaffolding are partly freed up for private graffiti, and works are commissioned and curated for public viewing. Selected alleys and laneways are opened up as hives of sub-culture activity in the night, with temporary installations, projections and nomadic bars. The aim is to give these sub-cultures a place in the life of the big city, and reverse the current alienation.

At the same time, there is much that can be done to reduce the graffiti in certain specific locations. In a fine situated design study, DOC designers proposed measures to minimize the graffiti and scratching that happens in buses. They realized that it is mainly the back third of the bus that is prone to damage, and proposed increased lighting and different seating arrangements (along the sides of the bus) that make the back of the bus less of a hiding place, much

easier to use, and generally a much more attractive place for law-abiding citizens than is currently the case.

This case shows resemblances with the grass pass design case in its future oriented approach and the development of the problem situation. Long existing counter measures were abandoned and new opportunities were explored. The problem as it presented itself was opened up by reconsidering the criminal character of these young graffiti makers. What is important to pick up here is the fact that although the problem presents itself as a single, big and difficult paradox, the solutions are many and varied. As conventional problem solving would have concentrated on addressing the problem-as-presented, without radical reframing, it would also have led to the attempt to create a singular and one-off intervention to solve it completely. The DOC designers arrived at a range of small interventions that all not so much completely solve the problem, but they contribute to ameliorating the situation dramatically.

ORGANIZATIONAL TRANSFORMATION

Next to the specific project results of these two social safety design cases, the potential contribution of design practice to this problem area can be explicated on a different organizational level. Although both cities were enthusiastic about the operational outcomes of the projects, they seemed to be even more inspired by the potential of this approach for all kinds of other problems their organizations are confronted with. The design process and outcomes immediately started them thinking about new issues and other areas of application. They were expressing suggestions like *"Could we do something similar with..."* *"Would you like to be involved with a project on..."* *"We should talk with... because I'm sure he is having a similar problem..."*

Without presenting design practice as a cure-all approach (these are just two examples of the application of design in a social safety context), these cases do illustrate the transforming potential of the design practice within this context. Reframing these long existing social safety paradoxes gives

organizations freedom of movement; it empowers them in situations they have their back to the wall. To put this observation into a management perspective; the organizations recognized the tactical potential of design practice next to the more obvious operational design outcomes on project level. This implies that these cases showed involved middle managers *how* they want to deal with similar issues in the future to enhance their organizations performance. It started them thinking about how to spend their budget and on what people to involve with new projects.

Although this is a very interesting observation, it is still a question whether the application of design practice on a tactical level within these organizations will contribute to better organizational performance in the long run. The impact of organizational decision-making on a tactical level may be too limited to make organizations actual paradox-proof. Where middle management recognizes the potential added value of design practice it is only able to translate this in terms of approaches and operational initiatives. The overall mission of the organization, the strategic organizational goals and the corporate identity (*what* do we stand for?) remain unaltered and conventionally problem-focused. Within such an unaltered strategic context design practice can surely offer promising palliatives. Designers can replace or at least complement existing management consultancy practices by offering a buy-in alternative approach for existing problem-solving approaches on a tactical level. But the elite group of management consultancy practice, the senior strategic consultants, have known for years that true organizational transformation can only be achieved by redeveloping the organization's vision. Traditional problem-solving approaches are so much embedded in corporate identities of organizations that there is a need for a far more strategical adoption of design practice. It is not unimaginable that the most promising contribution of design practice to social safety is on a much higher organizational level than was described in these two design cases. Is design possibly the answer to major organizational problems? Can these "design thinking like" approaches substitute existing management methods

to resolve major organizational paradoxes? The answer to these questions is most probably "no". The massive body of literature that covers organizational decision making and organizational change demonstrates the complexity, versatility and diversity of this potential field of application of design methods. It would be rather naïve to expect design to offer an instant solution for all these issues. However, design practice could offer a complementary approach to stir up organization transformation when traditional approaches get stuck. Design could inspire different disciplines to reconsider their traditional way of thinking and propose complementary methods like design-thinking literature is currently proposing.

Conversely, at this point, it is uncertain whether design practice, as it stands now, is already equipped for adoption on a strategic organizational level. The safe society case studies in this paper demonstrate the added value of these design approaches on a practical level but actual organizational change is a completely different area of application. Therefore, in future research, the potential contribution of design practice to organizational change should be explored and evaluated. Case studies in which design is applied on a more strategic level should reveal the true impact of these design thinking approaches for organizational transformations.

CONCLUSION

Altogether, the design perspective on social safety is based on key elements of actual design practice. The involved designers an approach that is very action oriented, and oriented towards the future. Instead of taking the social safety problem situation as a given, designers try to open it up by exploring the various perspectives and themes surrounding the problem. Eventually they are able to come to grips with the problem by framing the problem situation altogether. In this sense, the design approach in the area of social safety is fundamentally different from the earlier approaches of criminologist and sociologist who tend to apply traditional analysis and problem-solving techniques to tackle these same issues.

Designers aim to create environments that facilitate and trigger social processes (Norman, 2002). Within the context of social safety, it is essential for designers to understand the causes of anti-social or criminal behavior in order to trigger the desired behavior with their design interventions. Within both design cases, designers collected a lot of information about the problem, its context and its stakeholders. Eventually they used to “case-knowledge” to redefine the problem space (“it’s a parking problem”) and the solution space (“coffee shops should be coffee cafes”) at the same time. In essence, the design perspective on social safety, is somewhere in between the technological-intervention perspective of criminologist and the social cohesion perspective of sociologists. This does not imply that the design approach is a substitute for these two existing bodies of research. Complementary, the design perspective on social design offers many opportunities for interdisciplinary research combining the social understanding to create the right technical intervention.

These first explorative cases already showed some interesting applications of the design approach within social safety. Within the two cases it became clear that the involved organizations recognized the tactical potential of design practice next to the more obvious operational design outcomes on project level. An interesting area for further research is the application of design on this more tactical or even strategic level within organizations.

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